

careables.org

Deliverable 5.2

Adoption, Exploitation & Sustainability Report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The project Made4You facilitates the design, development and dissemination of open DIY healthcare through local co-design events and a global platform to share self-made healthcare products. With this document, we present our sustainability strategy, in order to ensure the adaptation, exploitation and longevity of the project outcomes. The project is operating under the name “Careables”, reflected in the online platform careables.org, the products shared on this platform, also called “careables”, as well as in the various project activities, such as local ideation and co-design sessions leading towards the development of careables. Thus, in the following document we will make reference only to Careables when speaking about the Made4You project, including all project activities¹.

While Careables is not a standard business endeavour but rather a combination of activities carried out by a consortium of partners it shares a set of characteristics with social businesses. Thus, we have chosen the social business model canvas as a guiding tool for drafting our *adaption, exploitation and sustainability strategy*.

In terms of exploitable outcome from the project we distinguish between the online tools, such as the platform, guidelines and materials to be offered online and made globally available, and the activities taking place in the physical world that need to be implemented locally. Therefore, we also distinguish between a global strategy and local chapters.

The value proposition of Careables clearly relates to patients and their families and care givers, health professionals, makers and designers. These are the beneficiaries of our project, while the range of stakeholders is much wider,

¹ Please note that Made4You remains the official EC-funded project title as changes in the naming was not possible after contract signature. However, we will use the name “careables” to refer to all project activities, as we aim to promote only this name.

including especially donors and philanthropic bodies who are understood as customers, supporting the project financially. In the second half of the project, both groups – the beneficiaries as well as the donors – are important contributors to the project’s progress. The first group – the Careables beneficiaries - will further support defining and bringing evidence for the project’s value and impact in the next months. The later – the Careables customers - will be involved in sharpening and assessing the sustainability model in economic terms. Therefore, we are elaborating a sponsoring model for those who want to give monetary support in the future. Another approach towards financial sustainability in the future that we will explore further is crowdfunding.

Most importantly, all partners are truly committed to the project goals and to work on a sustainable model to make Careables the preferred platform, all over the world, to find and create open, inspiring healthcare solutions and methods, transferable to local contexts.

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List of abbreviations

DIY	Do It Yourself
EC	European Commission
ECG	Electrocardiography
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement No. 780298 with the European Commission
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V.
IP	Intellectual Property
IPRs	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KUL	KU Leuven
OD	Fab Lab Opendot
TOG	Together to Go
Waag	Waag – Technology and Society
WP	work package (usually with the number, e.g. WP1, WP2, etc.)
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (en: Centre for Social Innovation)

1. Introduction

The aim of this report is to reflect on the experiences, which we gained during the events and project activities performed during the first 18 months, and present ideas of how to expand the experiences beyond the current groups, leading Careables towards a sustainable open healthcare service in the future.

We will discuss different models, such as collaborations with companies and NGOs, crowdfunding, models for donations, or social franchising and explore how these models could be implemented in the context of Careables and what the implications of any such model could be.

In a brainstorming session during the consortium meeting in Milano, in February 2019, the consortium collected ideas on what the future of Careables could look like and identified important elements as well as creative ideas:

Figure 1: Brainstorming on Careables sustainability

As shown in Figure 1, different factors need to be taken into consideration when we think about the sustainability of project results:

First, Careables has a wide set of outcomes and activities, such as: the platform itself with the repository of the Open Healthcare Map; the toolkits on how to organise the co-design process and the engagement events; the experiences from the Careables hackathons and other capacity building activities that can be shared with others; and finally, the trainings in prototyping technologies, the legal advice and the global community channels.

Second, we work in a strong but diversified partnership: Careables consists of a diverse consortium of different organisations with different modes of operation, diverse social business goals, etc. Thus, exploitation opportunities vary across the partners and need to be considered accordingly.

To guide our work towards sustainability and exploitation we decided to work with an alternate version of the business model canvas for social businesses or non-profit businesses. Although Careables is not yet a social business as such, there are a lot of elements of a social business represented in our aims and objectives.

Thus, this deliverable is structured along the building blocks of the social business model canvas, starting with an introduction of the tool itself. It should also be mentioned that this is a first attempt to define the potentials of exploitation and create a sustainable vision for Careables – at a stage where there are still a lot of uncertainties. D5.4 Final Dissemination and Sustainability Report, which will be delivered at the end of the project, will follow up on the plans that are presented in this document and discuss the concrete commitment of each partner in the execution of the exploitation of project results, the possible adoption of the Careables results by others and a sustainable continuation of the most promising outcomes.

2. Social Business Model Canvas

The social business model canvas² is a variation of the well-known business model canvas, first introduced by Alexander Osterwalder as a strategic management tool, which is widely used for start-ups. The social business model canvas, created by the Social Innovation Lab, is slightly different, as it focuses on supporting specifically social businesses and non-profit ventures. It supports us in how we approach our sustainability planning.

Social Innovation Lab

Social Business Model Canvas				
Key Resources <small>What resources will you need to run your activities? People, finance, access?</small>	Key Activities <small>What programme and non-programme activities will your organisation be carrying out?</small>	Type of Intervention <small>What is the format of your intervention? Is it a workshop? A service? A product?</small>	Segments <small>Beneficiary</small> <hr/> <small>Customer</small>	Value Proposition <hr/> <small>Social Value Proposition</small> <small>Impact Measures</small> <hr/> <small>How will you show that you are creating social impact?</small> <small>Customer Value Proposition</small>
Partners + Key Stakeholders <small>Who are the essential groups you will need to involve to deliver your programme? Do you need special access or permissions?</small>	<small>What programme and non-programme activities will your organisation be carrying out?</small>	Channels <small>How are you reaching your beneficiaries and customers?</small>	<small>Who are the people or organisations who will pay to address this issue?</small>	<small>What do your customers want to get out of this initiative?</small>
Cost Structure <small>What are your biggest expenditure areas? How do they change as you scale up?</small>		Surplus <small>Where do you plan to invest your profits?</small>	Revenue <small>Break down your revenue sources by %</small>	

Inspired by The Business Model Canvas

Figure 2: Social Business Model Canvas

As shown in Fig 2. the social business model canvas has 13 building blocks and different entry points. Similar to the business model canvas it is recommended to start thinking about the types of interventions and key activities that one plans to offer (the type of product that will deliver the value) and work from there towards the other segments, defining the target groups, here called segments, the value proposition, etc. In the case of the social business model, the field “segments” is divided into “beneficiaries” and “customers” as these might be two

²<http://www.socialbusinessmodelcanvas.com/wp-content/uploads/Social-Business-Model-Canvas.png>

different groups. Those benefiting from the social value might not necessarily be those paying for it. Accordingly, the value proposition itself is also divided into two elements, the social value (for the beneficiaries and society in general) and the customer value. For social businesses it might also be important to think about strategic stakeholders, in addition to the partners. And finally, for the social business model canvas the component “surplus” has been added to describe how and where possible profits would be invested.

While some of these components are still difficult to define at this stage of the Careables project, we find the canvas a helpful guide in structuring our exploitation and sustainability planning. Though it would also be helpful to create one canvas for each partner or for each activity cluster, with this report we try to cover the whole project in one canvas. In the following chapters we will elaborate the main building blocks of the social business model canvas and start with the key activities and objectives.

3. Key activities/key objectives

Our vision:

By 2025 Careables is the preferred platform, all over the world, to find and create open, inspiring healthcare solutions and methods, transferable to local contexts.

Our objectives:

- Build an ecosystem, linking existing local communities of citizens with disabilities and their families, healthcare professionals and makers and establish collaboration between these separate communities to develop their own open source and license interventions.
- Provide access to open source and digital fabrication tools enabling citizens with disabilities and healthcare professionals, in co-creation with designers and makers (DIY communities and maker spaces) to create customized self-made solutions to improve quality of life or services provided.
- Improve the accessibility of open source products; co-production of products that are tailored to people with special needs or disabilities as

well as healthcare professionals and bypassing the limitations of the classical industrial production.

- Provide an open accessible methodology to enable others to organise the context that supports the creation process of DIY healthcare products.
- Foster the ecosystem through open exchange of knowledge, case stories and manuals. Within the DIY approach, local production and global knowledge sharing is key.
- Build guidelines that allow anyone to replicate formats everywhere, considering the socio-technical aspects as well as relevant legal and regulatory frameworks, quality standards, IPR implications, security, safety and privacy issues.

The long-term goal is to affiliate a community of designers, users, fablabs and maker spaces who develop similar projects and replicate events and activities in various cities all around Europe or even globally. This process will produce a critical mass of projects that can be used and build upon, as well as a knowledge-sharing platform that aims to achieve mass adoption and global impact.

4. Types of Interventions

In the following chapter we will describe which types of our products will deliver value to our beneficiaries and customers.

Careables provides self-made solutions for people with disabilities and other healthcare needs that can be replicated. As a method, Careables fosters a proactive attitude and empowerment for users with healthcare needs to come to their own solutions. It does so by

- providing inspiring solutions,
- providing skills and knowledge,
- facilitating online and offline collaboration and creation of ideas and
- connecting with other communities and individuals, locally and globally.

The project is developing different types of interventions, services, and products that all contribute to the vision and objectives as described above.

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In this report, we don't cover the creation and sustainability of individual Careable products, but focus on the underlying processes and skills as well as the Careables platform.

4.1. Careables platform

The Careables consortium provides a platform for documenting and sharing healthcare solutions, which also includes the Open Healthcare Map, a collection of open DIY healthcare solutions: <https://www.welder.app/careables>

The platform consists of two tools to help open hardware development in healthcare: a documentation tool to make documentation of projects easier and a repository of projects to show the variety of open hardware projects in healthcare.

The platform is hosted by the partner Wevolver and is developed to be an Open Source Open Hardware platform, which means it can be used, hosted, inspected and adapted by anyone. This is an important step for the consortium to support the broader open hardware community.

careables.org

Hardware For Healthcare

Careables enables citizens to co-design and deliver people-centered health products through digital fabrication.

www.careables.org

LEARNING/COMMUNICATION MOBILITY OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS INDOOR INSTALLATIONS SELF CARE THERAPY DAILY LIVING

FLipMouse 5
A computer mouse you can control with your mouth or fingertips.
Careables Daily Living Fun/Leisure

Light Doorbell 6
Maybe you don't hear your doorbell ring, but you can see it as the light goes on. .
Careables Daily Living Indoor Installations

Custom Assistive Spoon 13
A spoon that adapts to any hand.
Careables Self Care

Lupo white cane tip 7
it's a custom made, 3D printed white cane tip.

Slimme pillendoos 7
De slimme pillendoos is ontwikkeld voor iemand met Parkinson.

Quali-fire 14
This speculative project aimed to use automated measurement to better understand the cause.

Figure 3: Screenshot of welder.app, the careables Open Hardware repository

The second part of the platform is the website, www.careables.org, that hosts everything besides the individual Careable project files. It shows events happening in the world, the knowledge base of our approach towards open healthcare, the results of our activities and in the next stage of the project also stories to inspire the global community. It should provide local community organizers with all the tools they need to create Careables events themselves. careables.org focuses on global outreach in English language as the local outreach and local information will always be found on the websites of the local partners to allow for easier adaptation.

4.2. Co-creation kit

We provide methods for the co-creation of healthcare solutions. The goal of providing these methods is to enable other communities and organisations to organise similar events, and to have some guidance and tools that support this ambition. The tools that have been used in the project have been provided in the form of a co-creation kit. Specifically coming from the lessons learned of Waag, the co-creation kit suggests a setup for a 6-8 sessions gathering of multidisciplinary stakeholders with the goal of successfully co-creating healthcare innovations. The setup of this document is already available³.

The format will now be improved by integrating new insights that are developed in the project and especially by the experiences from the other project partners. It will also be directly published on the careables.org website.

4.3. Training and Capacity Building

During local training and capacity building sessions, open resources are created to spread the acquired knowledge and make it exploitable globally. We are working to include the co-design methodology and digital fabrication technology in the curriculum of design and healthcare schools. We also see a demand to train DIY developers on legal and ethical requirements and started this through conference presentations.

On the local level, each partner is creating and experimenting with slightly different co-creation programmes, to gather insight into which methodology is locally most useful. Results, lessons learned and materials are published in the Careables knowledge base. The knowledge base is an online repository for sharing our knowledge, guidelines and tools. We want to offer our lessons learned during the project to the wider community and inspire others to replicate local activities, such as training and capacity building sessions.

³ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CfSs7kX2klq6miK6Drva1EXolmKjLRW0W22EKzjr-ys/>

Open Health HACKademy (Berlin)

Initially, we ran Careables Meetups for the ideation of DIY healthcare solutions and the sensitisation to the topic in the Berlin Fablab, followed by open workshop sessions for prototyping. We found out that especially students from quite diverse disciplines – like engineering, design but also social sciences and medical fields – were reachable, curious, and most importantly willing to contribute more time into the development of careables. However, they seemed to need a format that is not as loose as open workshop-hours to drop in and out and allows for a deeper involvement than a brainstorming session. We learned that ideally the co-creation process would be connected to the students' curriculum so they would have an extra gain by earning credit points.

Therefore, we designed the Open Health HACKademy, in cooperation with enABLE and MatchMyMaker, as a format to cater to the needs of students, but at the same time being openly accessible to professionals with an interest in this field and to those in need for healthcare solutions - no matter which age and background they have.

At the Open Health HACKademy, interdisciplinary teams with students from different disciplines, people with disabilities and makers jointly develop open source hardware solutions. It is an educational program that takes place in the semester break and that we offer in collaboration with universities like the TU Berlin (Technical University Berlin) and the HPI (Hasso-Plattner-Institute, University of Software Engineering in Potsdam).

The development teams are accompanied and supported by experienced coaches from the fields of electronic prototyping, coding, digital fabrication, and design thinking. They support the teams in working along the design process and getting basic technological knowledge. Additional knowledge like an introduction to the conceptual framework of open source hardware development, co-creative teamwork, and design thinking is given in short inputs.

Overall, the event combines:

- Learning about and actively applying co-design and open source hardware development.
- Hands-on experiences and engagement with inclusion, accessibility and diversity.

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- Introduction to methods of design thinking and user-centred project work.
- Practical project work with various teams.

The participants (including the users with specific needs) have several benefits:

- Experiencing creative collaboration in various teams with students from different departments, experts and users.
- Working on complex fabrication and health care issues and independently developing prototypical solutions.
- Gaining insights into electronic prototyping, coding, digital fabrication, and open source hardware development.
- Applying the participants' study skills in a practical project.
- Performing user-centred product development – from problem definition to prototype development.
- Applying methods of design thinking, as well as its mind-set.
- Benefiting from the positive experience of directly supporting somebody in need.

Health&Care Summer School (Milano)

A similar format to exploit in the future is the Health&Care Summer School. Following a comparable approach and structure as the HACKademy, OpenDot organized the Health&Care Summer School, an intensive, very practical and free training course with a focus on "Design for care". The aim of the Summer School was to develop concrete and simple solutions for the needs of people with disabilities through the co-design methodology developed with the Together to Go foundation.

The Health&Care Summer School was organised together with the Distributed Design Market Platform (DDMP), a European project fostering the role of emerging creatives. It took place in Milan over two weekends, 8-9 June and 22-23 June 2019.

The Health&Care Summer School engaged 16 participants and foresaw:

- Lectures in compelling topics such as certification about custom-made medical devices, co-design methodology, design for all, narratives for health&care projects, the importance of aesthetics,

- Co-design activities as a team: practical sessions for multidisciplinary teams working together with need-knowers.
- Trainings on digital fabrication technologies.

Training for healthcare professionals (Milano)

In addition to the Summer School, OpenDot tested out different training and engagement formats specifically targeted towards healthcare professionals. The most responsive groups within this category of professionals are the rehabilitation therapists, occupational therapists and orthopaedic technicians. Doctors and surgeons have been less responsive to our offers so far. In personal talks with the target group we learned that, in general, health care professionals understand the value of the DIY healthcare innovations, but they think it's not up to them to know how to use them.

The first Careables training course for health professionals focused on 3D printing based on joint reflections with the target group. Important factors influencing the training focus on 3D printing were the need to concentrate on the most relevant digital technologies first and the accessibility of the technology. Electronics and coding (e.g. Arduino, Raspberry Pi, etc.) are technologies healthcare professionals are even less familiar with. They are often requested to build something with non-technological tools and it is less common for them to deal with microcontroller or electronics. Also, 3D printers are small and very versatile, thus the hospital or the workshop doesn't require a big investment to start. Still the focus on technology was important as only speaking about co-design, design thinking, problem-solving and design methods would be too vague and does not offer enough clear benefits for the target group.

A very relevant aspect for the success of this kind of initiative is a certification or being part of official courses of a healthcare training supplier. In fact, OpenDot was involved by "Affidabile – formazione continua s.r.l.s", a company specialized in organizing and managing training programs in the healthcare sector. Beside the recognisability, the company is an accredited training organization for this specific target and participants who successfully complete the course can obtain certification and credits for their on-going professional training as requested by the Italian system.

After the success of the first 3D printer training, OpenDot will organize a second edition of “3D printing in Healthcare” and proposed an advanced course, too.

Another evolution of this first training program is the development of an online program, with webinars and toolkits that can be downloaded by participants. This material should be ready within 6 months after the end of the project.

The natural evolution of these technology-oriented training programs are co-design workshops in which people with diverse backgrounds, languages, methods, and mind-sets work together. During the last five years OpenDot and TOG have developed and refined a co-design in health&care method to guide makers, healthcare professionals and care receiver to effectively create personalised healthcare solutions.

All these activities can be replicated easily and will be part of the sustainability of the project, also leading to the development of more careables.

Waag Trainings (Amsterdam)

In Amsterdam, several activities have focussed on the knowledge transfer towards education. This has been done through semester-long courses in cooperation with the University of Applied Sciences in Amsterdam. These courses were part of the regular curriculum. Through Careables we provided a case (specific healthcare need) or allowed a perspective, in which a case could be identified for students and others to work on. This way people didn't only contribute to open healthcare innovation, but they were taught skills and guided in a process of how to practically apply them.

An example of a case provided to the students was the Squeez-a-ball project. The project originated from the first OpenCall program that was hosted by Waag. It foresaw the development of a pain sensor based on squeezing an object instead of ticking the classical 10-point likert-scale box. 12 groups of students were asked to work on a use case and interface for this feature. Results varied from an interface to deal with phantom-pain in a missing limb, to an indicator of when women should go to the hospital in the process of giving birth.

Another way we tried to integrate the Careables perspective in an educational setting was through the university study programme called “care-technology”. This set of courses (minor) embraces a multidisciplinary approach by pairing

students from care specific curriculums with more technically oriented students. Instead of giving them an assignment, these students explored existing needs to focus on. One of these groups created a prototype for ECG measuring through an ultra-sensitive wearable sensor. A second group focused on developing a way to make walking stairs more accessible for elderly people.

A third training activity was focused on teachers. The University of Applied Sciences acknowledges the relevance of digital fabrication and has set up a masterclass program for teachers to develop their understanding of digital fabrication technologies. To enhance this masterclass, Careables was suggested as a case to make things a bit more practical. Four teachers took part in this training and worked on a re-design for an open source prosthetic device and an alternative for a finger splint measuring device. Both projects were documented on the Careables platform and contributed to the fine-tuning of the Careables documentation tool.

Although the teachers succeeded in providing documentation for their Careable designs one important lesson from the training sessions at Waag is the need to motivate and support participants further in properly contributing to the open source knowledge creation. This is a challenge for the documentation tool development as well as for the training programme itself. Documentation and knowledge sharing needs to be further implemented in the curriculum.

A second challenge is the complexity or perceived complexity of involving real world cases. Especially the students have grown accustomed to working on assignments within the walls of the university, working with peers and teachers along the way. We noticed that it takes quite some effort to make students work with people outside academia and focus on their very personal and real-life issues. It takes students outside their comfort zone and proved to need extra attention to make sure that students don't work on solutions in perfect isolation from the real world.

Careables at GIG Hubs

Taking the experiences from the three main partner hubs we now form the programmes in three additional hubs from the Global Innovation Gathering network. This includes working

- with Communitere Nepal⁴ in Kathmandu to be involved in their Humanitarian Design Challenge created with FieldReady⁵ that involves local communities and capacity building;
- with Kumasi Hive⁶ in Ghana to conduct a co-design and training programme on assistive technology with university students and disability organisations;
- with the Science Camp in Basra⁷, Iraq to work on prostheses and a potentially more spaces.

In this way, during the second half of the project, the platform, co-creation toolkit and training materials will be tested, adapted and expanded to ensure global knowledge exchange and transferability to local contexts.

4.4. Legal guidelines

Within Careables, the key legal issues in co-producing open source healthcare solutions as well as the ethical and legal aspects concerning the execution of the project are analysed as part of the Ethical and Legal Work package (WP6 'Ethical and Legal Aspects'). The outcome of such analysis is substantiated in project deliverables, namely 'D6.1 Legal and ethical inventory and in-depth analysis'; D6.2 'Implementation of the legal and ethical requirements'; D6.3 'Validation and policy recommendations'.

These deliverables are aimed to provide ethical and legal guidance not only to the consortium partners for the execution of the project, but also to users, makers, designers, caregivers, and healthcare practitioners – and more generally, any stakeholder – that will be involved in the co-design and co-production of careables.

⁴ <https://nepal.comunitere.org/>

⁵ <https://www.fieldready.org/>

⁶ <https://vc4a.com/kumasi-hive/>

⁷ <https://www.facebook.com/Iraqimakerspace%20%20/>

Furthermore, within the context of WP5, a white paper (D5.3 'White paper on legal guidelines') will be delivered at the end of the second year of the project. The document will tackle the possible approaches to address legal aspects and related constraints for the co-design and co-production of open source healthcare solutions.

In the light of the primary findings contained in D6.1⁸, the ethical and legal guidance provided so far within Careables focus in the matter of:

- Privacy and Data Protection: this field of law is transversal to the whole project as well as for its exploitation phase, with respect in particular to the following aspects:
 - The careables.org platform and repository must be implemented to comply with the key principles of data protection law, namely lawfulness, fairness, and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimization; accuracy; storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality as enshrined in art. 5 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)).
 - Co-design and co-creation sessions: the organization of such initiatives must be lawfully performed with respect to the processing of personal data: key legal requirements of GDPR concerning for instance information and consent and the exercise of data subjects rights have to be duly be taken into account by the organisers of events.
 - The careables: The development of the careables themselves, whether entailing in future the processing of personal data, must respect GDPR legal requirements. Of most relevance to this regard are obligations that require setting up secure processing of personal data (as of art. 32 GDPR) and the so-called principle of 'data protection by design' (art. 35 GDPR).
- Intellectual Property law: the co-creation and co-design of open healthcare solutions entail also intellectual property issues, that range from third-

⁸ For an extensive overview of such findings and for a more complete legal analysis of the issues related to the careables and careables.org, see D6.1.

party patent protection on certain items to the licensing of project designs within the careables.org platform.

- Liability and Tort law: to promote the development of careables and the diffusion thereof, it is of key importance that stakeholders understand their role and responsibilities from the onset of their involvement. Aspects such as safety and security and the related liability for the reproduction of careables (such as through fabrication tools or via 3D printing) need to be assessed under a liability and tort law perspective.

Having also regard to the above-mentioned legal matters, the 'White Paper on legal guidelines' will elaborate on theoretical notions provided in the project deliverable as well as legal research carried out to such extent with all practical instances presented by stakeholders. The White Paper will be written in a clear and plain language in order to reach as much as possible a wide array of stakeholders (from individuals to makers and designers, to healthcare practitioners, etc.). Possible approaches to address legal aspects in co-producing open source healthcare solutions will be outlined.

5. Segments

The Social Business Canvas distinguishes between “beneficiaries” and “customers”. This division is based on the fact that beneficiaries may gain value from the interventions without having to pay for it, while customers are regarded as those contributing financially. In the following chapter we will outline our beneficiaries and customers.

5.1 The beneficiaries

We gave a comprehensive overview of our three main target groups and communities in the Deliverables D1.1 Engagement strategy and the D5.1 Awareness raising, outreach, and dissemination strategy. Our most crucial beneficiaries are:

5.1.1 The users/patients

In a healthcare context, users are usually called patients. We prefer to refer to this group as “users”, because many people within this target group do not

consider themselves as “patients” in most of their daily lives. Being a “patient” has the connotation of having very little agency to many users, and also to many members of our team. In contrast, we believe in the agency of every user. Being actively involved as users in the co-design of solutions can bring not only to the products that are being developed, and to the development of participatory design processes, but also to the users’ lives. These effects are augmented within the Careables context, as sometimes users are also makers or designers within the scope of this project.

Following the definition of positive health by Huber⁹, we also include emotional and social wellbeing into the scope of Careables. Therefore, our users can be:

- People with healthcare needs
- Their caregivers
- User groups, patient groups
- People facing physical, emotional or social challenges
- Humanitarian support groups related to health and care challenges

5.1.2 The healthcare professionals

Healthcare professionals are often in contact with cutting edge technologies. It is in fact, one of the first fields where advanced innovations get in contact with a wide public. Digital fabrication could end up being the last gizmo bought by a hospital to implement their productivity or efficiency. Careables aims to involve healthcare professionals by introducing them to co-design, human-centred design and open technologies that are easier to use and adjust, cheaper and can be largely diffused amongst different target groups.

During the training activities and co-design sessions with health care professionals, it was noticeable how this approach triggered the interest of participants due to the possibilities offered by the technologies.

Health care professionals in our project can be:

- General practitioners

⁹ Huber M, Knottnerus JA, Green L, Horst H van der, Jadad AJ, Kromhout D, et al. How should we define health? BMJ. 2011;343(4163):235–7. Available online: <https://www.bmj.com/content/343/bmj.d4163.full> (last checked on 17.12.2018)

- Doctors/specialists
- Therapists
- Nurses
- Humanitarian support groups related to health and care challenges

5.1.3 The makers

Makers are a community of engineering and technology-based DIY practitioners who also utilize hacker practices, i.e. often combine hardware and software approaches to create new devices. Much of their work is focused on open source hard- and software in the fields of electronics, robotics, 3D-printing, metal- and woodworking, often implementing aspects of art and crafts.

The maker target group for Careables includes:

- Makers
- Designers
- Engineers
- General innovators for generating ideas
- Maker spaces
- Maker communities

5.2 The customers

Some of the above-mentioned target groups can be regarded as beneficiaries and as customers, where the difference is that the latter are expected to pay for the value they get from the project. E.g. a healthcare professional, who participates in a training on how to use digital fabrication tools to support clients, may be a customer of our training offers – and if it is not him individually then probably his/her employer. Likewise, makers might become customers of Careables in case they will use the platform in the future to promote their DIY healthcare solutions, if we would allow for a subscription model.

Public social sector institutions, foundations and potential donors are, however, currently considered the most important customer segments. The engagement of these target groups is crucial in order to secure long-term funding for the Careables platform, funding for projects in the wider ecosystem and funding for individuals who create careables.

Public social sector and healthcare industry

Due to the differences in organising the healthcare sector in different countries we combine the sometimes publicly organized and the privately organized institutions into one customer segment. We then see on a case-by-case or country-by-country basis where we can best attract paying customers.

This can be:

- Hospitals
- Health insurances
- Care homes
- Health and social management sector
- Prostheses manufacturers
- Medical stores
- Pharmaceutical companies

Institutional Donors

We plan to mobilise institutional donors for a set of Careables-related activities. For example, in the future there will be a need to further develop Careables related projects, such as tools to support the co-creation for special needs; there will be a need to fund or co-sponsor specific trainings or to fund the creation and incubation of individual careables. A successful example of these fundraising efforts is the project “Match my Maker”, that got funded through the Google Impact Challenge Germany and is working close with the Careables team to create a matchmaking tool for makers and people with disabilities to create careables together.

The group of donors include:

- Private corporations
- Foundations
- NGOs
- Governmental Organisations (all levels)
- International Governmental Organisations (e.g. WHO, UNHCR, DESA)

Individual Donors

With the further development of the platform, we can address individuals that are also represented in the three main target groups of beneficiaries or are supporters of our beneficiaries, for small donations. Donations could be asked for sustaining the platform or for local activities of project partners or a wider global community alike.

In addition, individual donors might be willing to fund teams who created careables with a market potential in setting up their own (social) businesses. We envision supporting specific campaigns for donations or crowdfunding of these individual careables (healthcare products).

6. Value proposition

Having introduced our beneficiaries and customers, we will now elaborate in more detail on the unique value proposition that Careables offers to them.

6.1 Social value proposition

When looking at the bigger picture, with our work we show that everyone – from users to professionals in the healthcare sector – can be a maker of healthcare devices and thus innovating healthcare. Supporting an independent way of life and lifestyle through products that are not necessarily medical devices but all kinds of small things to increase the well-being of people is possible nowadays. This is one of the goals of our general awareness raising campaign that Careables aims to achieve through outreach and dissemination.

More specifically, looking at the three main beneficiary groups, we see benefits from the knowledge and enhanced mutual understanding that is created through co-design sessions, trainings and events – and from resources that are shared as open knowledge.

The users / patients

Users, also known as patients, benefit from the services and personalized products that may have not been previously accessible, either due to lack of

access to resources or lack of know-how. Our users tend to be unfamiliar with the possibilities of digital fabrication or lack the support and confidence to start developing their own open hardware products. Opening up maker spaces for this specific user group, in the physical and the digital world, offers them access to previously unknown resources.

Our approach of co-creation changes the power relationship for patients. They do not necessarily have to wait until they are provided with a solution from an authority in the healthcare sector. They can develop their own personalized devices and tools, and by that getting empowered through the process of addressing their own needs.

Careables helps with creating a more patient-centred methodology of innovation in contrast to only looking into what is technically possible.

The healthcare professionals

This group benefits from the improvement of processes, approaches, tools and solutions in the healthcare sector thanks to digital fabrication technologies and the co-design methodology.

Although many factors discourage innovation in health and care contexts such as bureaucracy, high workload, budget lines and leadership system, an increasing number of pioneering individuals – especially those working directly with patients – and organisations are making use of tools to improve the way they address the users' needs. It is important to underline that technologies and tools don't replace scientific skills or medical knowledge, but simplify processes, help in the materialization of ideas, and allow professionals to deliver customized solutions for users.

As the TOG foundation's experience shows, innovation requires 1) concrete needs to be resolved in the everyday practices, 2) an inventive mind-set and 3) time to understand how technologies work and what they can do. An inspiring example has been the co-production and replication of a tricycle for a 6-year-old who suffers from a complex neurological pathology that makes most daily actions difficult. Our two partners TOG and the Fablab Opendot teamed up to engage in co-design, customization and rapid prototyping to produce a tricycle with reduced cranks, ergonomic saddle, support for the back and adjustable handlebar. The 3D model is customized for this patient but can be quickly

adapted to the needs of other children with different disabilities, using personal digital fabrication. In the Netherlands a replication of the bike has been made in the Fablab of WAAG, showing the potential dispersion of 'open' healthcare solutions.

The makers

Makers, aligned with the maker movement will be able to have a secure and supportive platform to generate and share their ideas. They will be supported with our co-creation tool kit, the knowledge platform and documentations of DIY health care products. Thus, makers benefit from open resources that allow to get inspiration for own projects and to learn new technologies. The platform helps to gain visibility for their own projects, potentially attracting financial contributors.

Essentially, the success and sustainability of the Careables platform and Careables projects depends on a thriving maker movement. This way new ideas relating to current and future Careables projects are being generated.

The software of the sharing and collaboration platform for careables.org is made open source. This enables any interested party for which the platform is relevant – from individuals to organizations – to 1) contribute to the software development, and 2) deploy their own instances of the platform and to use parts of the code to develop their own custom platforms. It provides further assurance to communities: they are not locked in by a closed platform that is dependent on a private company, they now to contribute to open knowledge, and at the same time they can use the provided platform to host their data securely and with low effort.

Impact measures

Validating Careables' impact within the involved communities and beyond is critical for the project itself and on a long-term perspective a key factor for the wider outreach of the Careables approach and its sustainability. Therefore, a separate deliverable, the D4.1 Impact Assessment Plan, has been created and will be followed up with the D 4.3 Impact Assessment Report at the end of the project. Impact assessment looks at the longer-term, deeper changes that have resulted from the project. While these aspects can often be measured only after

the project ended, the project tries to find evidence that indicates such changes to take place.

Aiming to facilitate the co-design of open healthcare for people with physical limitations and uniting a community of makers, healthcare professionals and people with physical limitations who develop and share a critical mass of careables, we defined five sub-objectives that relate to 1) the accessibility and usefulness of the Careables platform, 2) the increased knowledge-sharing and 2) cooperation amongst the stakeholders as well as the 4) documentation and replication of careables and finally to the 5) improved quality of life of participants (see D4.1. for more details).

Each of these objectives includes one or several of the beneficiaries / customers mentioned above.

Priority in our evaluation and impact assessment is put on the increased accessibility to Careables for our users/patients. Regular evaluation activities to assess these aspects are foreseen throughout the project, via a combination of qualitative “walkthroughs” through our platform, as well as quantitative instruments like questionnaires and usage statistics.

Subsequently, we want to understand the project’s impact on knowledge and skills of the participants involved (users, makers, healthcare professionals). This can be knowledge resulting from the co-creation process as well as the creation, documentation and sharing of careables. This knowledge is expected to be manifold and covers changes in understandings, awareness, attitudes, practices and policies.

In addition, we aim to better understand on how to stimulate the creation and sharing of new knowledge between our stakeholder groups, which closely links to better understanding how the collaboration between the stakeholder groups can be fostered.

Finally, the effect that we expect to settle in the long-term is an improved quality of life of participants. While this concept is certainly influenced by a range of aspects that are beyond the scope of our project, we nevertheless expect that participants will, in the long-term, benefit from their involvement in our project or the usage of careables in one or more of the dimensions of quality of life (WHOQOL, 1995): like physical and psychological aspects, independence, social

relationships or the environment of users, like home environment or physical security. With the aim to capture the project influence on these aspects, we will organize interviews with lead users, who were involved in the development process of careables. We will collect feedback on Careables' impact, as well as drivers and barriers experienced during the co-design process. Also the feedback on the Careables platform itself will be investigated with regard to the dimensions of quality of life mentioned above.

So potential indicators that we want to bring evidence for are:

- Increased capability of the involved participants to support the creation of individualised, adapted, affordable health care solutions.
- Increased knowledge on the fabrication process of health devices.
- Citizens' increased awareness, sense of ownership and responsibility for the creation of health care devices.
- Changes in attitudes of citizens with regards to health and well-being.
- Improved collaboration between users (citizens with physical limitations, carers and healthcare professionals), makers (engineers, designers, fabricators), private corporations & donors, and public sector.
- Changes in the time spent by users in persuading friends, relatives or fellow workers about the support in creating health care solutions.
- Reduced social isolation of persons with physical limitations.
- Number of bottom-up health care devices created, number of documentations put online, number of experiences shared and ideas taken up.
- Increased number of citizens being engaged with the creation of health care devices for a higher well-being.

At the end of the project, the diversified stakeholders involved in the Careables project will be provided with an "easy to use" toolkit to continuously assess the project impact on individuals and involved communities alike. The toolkit will consist of selected, defined performance metrics and a handbook including instruments on how to assess these.

6.2 Customer Value Proposition

The value we create for users, makers and healthcare professionals is also the biggest selling point for donors, foundations and public social institutions.

Public social sector and healthcare industry

The healthcare sector (public and private), along with academics, healthcare practitioners and researchers, will benefit from the research and innovation brought through the Careables platform (through careables projects).

Health care in general is very expensive, as individual solutions need manual labour of highly skilled and certified professionals. If individualisation through digital fabrication techniques would be included in the general health system, it should be possible to reduce the cost of innovation in public healthcare system.

We see benefits if healthcare professionals are more proactive as the open innovation approach has already led to more effective hospital structures and more start-ups created around them.¹⁰

The value for the public social sector and healthcare industry includes:

- Experimenting with new approaches in the public healthcare system
- Fostering a changing mind-set that enables and drives innovation in health and care
- Redistributing risks and benefits of the healthcare solution development

Donors and sponsors

Donors and sponsors will be able to fulfil their social responsibility and to make their communities, along with the global society, a better place through the hardware technologies facilitated by Careables makers and contributors. Furthermore, institutional donors and sponsors will benefit from an increased

¹⁰ <https://www.nicklauschildrens.org/> and <https://www.miamiherald.com/news/business/biz-monday/article139483378.html>

visibility in the Careables community through advertisements and the relation to the Careables platform.

When applying for open calls of foundations we can show the already established knowledge base, communities and platform that is the result of the Careables initiative and leads to more professional and effective projects.

For private donors we provide the opportunity to do good with a dedicated and clear goal, for a definable and comprehensible cause. It also gives the social network of our users the opportunity to support their friend/family members; or to drive projects that have a very personal interest for individual donors (e.g. because they themselves or their peers are touched by a problem that is addressed with a careable).

To attract private donations, we think of

- Fundraising campaigns to attract small donations (this is mainly possible for the charitable partners of the Careables consortium)
- Crowdfunding campaigns where participants get a reward in return for their monetary support

At the same time we are aware that promoting crowdfunding campaigns for private health care needs is still a rarely applied practice and we will learn from testing this approach.

7. Channels

In the following chapter we will present the channels that will be used by the project to communicate our products and value proposition to beneficiaries, customers and cooperation partners.

In the deliverable D5.1 we laid out how to reach our target groups, beneficiaries and customers alike. Crucial part of this is our stepwise strategy to address people, from being only interested into becoming involved in the project; our strategy is based on local and global outreach activities that take place via online and offline channels.

The most important global channel for finding, creating and contributing to the project is our Careables platform. To bring people to the platform we actively

reach out on social media. With the relaunch of the careables.org website we will also offer the opportunity of online advertisement.

Next to our own channels, and the channels of all the project partners, we work to form partnerships with suitable initiatives to be featured on their media.

For the long-term sustainability of Careables we highlight a few ambitions of our activities:

- Stimulate local groups to self-organize meetings on a volunteer basis or with self-acquired funding.
- Have regular open days in labs and maker spaces that work on health-related projects worldwide.
- Find ambassadors and a committed developer community.
- Contribute to open hardware events and enable communities to include health and care as one of their focus topics.

The implementation of community building strategy during the first half of the project clearly showed that some changes in how to attract and engage people were necessary. We found e.g. that not even in a big city like Berlin there are enough people committed to joining monthly meetups that centre only on open hardware in health and care. Therefore, the monthly Careables meetup was reformed to the more focused HACKAcademy program and to a broader Berlin Open Hardware meetup. Connecting with other makerspaces, hackerspaces and Fablabs to promote Careables is very important. As we have seen, similar experiences were made across the three main locations, Berlin, Amsterdam and Milano.

In terms of promotion material there are also important lessons learned from the first year, which we need to consider. To change the mindset at healthcare institutions, and therefore for example get included in the 'treatment' at general practitioners, we see that print is still the most important channel. Thus, we plan to pilot a brochure that we want to spread in every doctor's office or therapy practice in one of the locations of our Careables partners.

8. Key resources

The next two chapters will introduce the key resources and partnerships that are the foundation of our work.

The resources needed for sustaining Careables outcomes differ across the interventions. All partners are very committed to continue their work in open hardware in health and care and to find funding sources and business models to allow to retain and attract expert personnel.

For all the parts of the projects, outreach and communication resources are needed to ensure dissemination to the appropriate communities.

Beneficiaries

Our main beneficiaries are also our most important resource. They often participate in the project as volunteers/on a pro bono basis. Careables needs case providers (expert users), healthcare professionals, makers and designers for the co-design process to work and therefore needs access to their communities and multipliers. We often find that our beneficiaries need financial resources to participate on a longer term in the Careables activities, especially to be motivated to also document their designs.

Platform and website

For the platform to be sustainable after the EC funding period it is important to have a partner committed to maintaining the platform and covering the server costs.

Wevolver supports the hosting and maintenance of Welder.app, the hardware repository and collaboration platform, for at least another 3 years after the project ended. This includes hosting, maintenance of the code, and support.

Wevolver also actively promotes the platform within its strong network within the open source hardware ecosystem. Lastly the platform benefits from cross pollination from Wevolver's own website and community which brings in traffic, users and projects.

OpenDot commits to support the hosting and maintenance of the careables.org website for at least another 3 years after the project ended, this includes hosting, maintenance, updating and uploading of contents. In addition, we envision the creation of new content important for the future of the platform.

Training, co-design events and meetups

Resources needed for continuing with events and trainings are mainly costs for personnel, which are well trained in the specific topic, well connected within the local community and have good communication and teaching skills. Additionally, access to locations that cater to the specific need for the event, e.g. labs with digital fabrication machines, are needed.

Legal guidelines

KU Leuven's commitment to the sustainability of Careables is proved through a strong engagement in the dissemination of research results. Research results concern the ethical and legal requirements and challenges related to the co-design and co-creation of careables (as briefly outlined above in section 4.4 'Legal guidelines' and more extensively in D6.1). In the context of careables events and initiatives, it has been noticed a genuine interest by different stakeholders – e.g. healthcare professionals, makers, designers, individuals with healthcare needs, etc. – on the ethical and legal requirements for the co-design or co-production of open healthcare solutions.

The stakeholder interest in these issues and matters has been testified by the many invitations that KUL, as ethical legal partner, has received for giving talks, presentations at conferences, seminars, workshops etc.¹¹ These activities include, among others, the Creative Commons Global Summit (Lisbon, 2019)¹²; the Open User Innovation Conference (Utrecht, 2019)¹³; the AAATE Conference – Global Challenges in Assistive Technology: Research, Policy & Practice (Bologna, 2019).¹⁴ In addition to these initiatives, the impact for sustaining the outcomes of careables will be enhanced through the dissemination of research results through publication of research findings in high level academic journals related

¹¹ The exhaustive list of dissemination initiatives and events will be provided in D5.4 – 'Final Dissemination and Sustainability Report' (M36).

¹² See <https://ccglobalsummit2019lisbonportugal.sched.com/event/MjHI/how-open-is-distributed-design-an-overview-about-the-distributed-design-market-platform-and-its-activities>.

¹³ See <https://sites.google.com/view/oui2019/>.

¹⁴ <https://aaate2019.eu/>.

to the field of law and healthcare, or law and innovative technologies (e.g. *Technology and Disability* etc.).

Finally, KUL is interested in being involved in future open hardware projects in order to further promote the knowledge and experience gained in careables.

9. Partners and key stakeholders

Careables is a service that can be delivered by the project partners and does not have any crucial dependencies from others. The consortium came together from the onset based on its genuine interest and complementary expertise and is thus the most important alliance for the Careables project.

However, we realise that partnerships are crucial for gaining visibility, reaching wider impact and, more generally, for sustaining the project activities in the long run. The consortium partners are all very well connected, locally and internationally, and contribute important networks to the sustainability strategy of Careables. Important partners and key stakeholders that we have already established contacts with include patient organisations, associations of disabled people, healthcare providers, hospitals, MedTech industry, maker communities, and maker networks, design organisations, philanthropical organisations, and platforms with a special focus on health and care related topics.

On more concrete terms, we started to set up a matrix where we identify concrete stakeholders and their connection to the aims and values of Careables. We call this matrix the *"worldwide inventory of organisations and communities active in open healthcare"*. The current database lists around 90 organisations and 40 platforms worldwide that are potentially relevant for us.

In order to transform this wide range of stakeholders into partners for Careables, we started brainstorming on specific partnership models for potential partners. These models include offers for collaborative actions for the different partners to make the cooperation relevant for both sides. Such models can range from specific training offers on co-creation and digital fabrication for healthcare professionals or hospitals to the creation of specific content or events, as well as the promotion of local donors or sponsors.

The ideas for activities that engage the various stakeholders are currently very broad and need to be defined in more concrete terms during the second half of

the project. For some of the options we are planning to create opportunities to run some pilots. These could include activities such as:

- Offer sponsorship for individual DIY healthcare solutions from our Careables co-creation sessions
- Address larger companies with CSR (cooperate social responsibility) programmes, or programmes that support the disability manager helping to develop careables for their own employees, e.g. as a team building measure in engineering companies
- Offer sheltered workshops for people with disabilities
- Organise hackaday contests
- Organise contests between users to design healthcare products
- Organise a project contest on a specific topic (call)
- Design calls for local involvement
- Participate in the European week of making
- Careables foundation handing out grants

Apart from these ideas, we have already launched cooperation and started to implement joint activities with some organisations. E.g. *MatchMyMaker*¹⁵ and *beAble*¹⁶ are closely cooperating with Careables in diverse activities in Berlin, such as the HACKademy or awareness raising events. With *enABLE*¹⁷ and *FieldReady*¹⁸ we have also established close contacts and are currently exploring future cooperation opportunities.

10. Cost structure

In this chapter we look into the biggest expenditure areas and how they are expected to change as we scale up. The experiences through the Careables activities provide helpful insights for future activities and how to budget future projects.

¹⁵ <http://matchmymaker.de/>

¹⁶ <https://be-able.info/de/be-able/>

¹⁷ <http://enablingthefuture.org/>

¹⁸ <https://www.fieldready.org/>

careables.org

Careables Platform

To maintain and host the welder.app platform with the careables repository, there are minimal costs that need to be covered:

- Server & Hosting Costs: 750 – 1,000 € per month (depending on the amount of user activity and its effect on storage and bandwidth usage)
- Maintenance (excluding development of new features) costs about 1,000 - 1,500 € per month

This amounts to 60,000 – 90,000 € for three years.

careables.org

We estimate costs of 20,000 € over the 3 years that include hosting, maintenance, Wordpress design and plugins. The editing, outreach, community management would need to be added.

Co-creation kit

The online representation is included in the Wordpress costs, the cost of creation are covered by the Careables budget.

Community engagement and local outreach

A big part of the budget is currently used for community involvement. We see that this part has quite high running costs as it can't be automated or scaled up as easily. Depending on the local cost of living and the experience of the staff, we would see around 4,800 - 5,500 € per month for one person to be employed by one of the partners, including ancillary wage costs.

HACKademy

3 week-ends, 20,000 €

In order to run an Open Health HACKademy or a similar program, sponsorships and additional funding is needed to cover costs like rent for the venue that should include a Fablab or similar open accessible tools and machines, material budgets for prototyping, catering, in cases accommodation, remuneration for coaches and organizers, compensations for voluntary mentors and external experts, as well as a budget for outreach and campaigning in order to make the

program known amongst the relevant stakeholder groups and finally to communicate the solutions that have been developed during the HACKademy.

A HACKademy deals with healthcare challenges of individuals with different levels and areas of complexity. Costs depend very much on the specific challenge but we estimate an average budget of 3,000 to 5,000 € for challenges of lower complexity (including coaching, materials, food).

Waag Prototyping series

The Open Call/prototyping series organised by Waag typically included 6-8 sessions. The starting costs for setting up this program and adjusting it were quite high as the whole concept had to be designed from scratch.

The costs for these sessions typically include the support for attendees in terms of personnel, rent of a suitable space, and material costs for prototyping. Additional costs that need to be considered relate to the promotion of the programme and the recruiting of participants. After running 3 series so far, we estimate that the cost of organising a new prototyping series will amount to around 40,000 €. This estimation is based on the assumption that no further training material needs to be developed, nor does it include the costs of acquisition.

Health&Care Summer School

The Summer School by OpenDot centres on *Design for care* and is about co-designing careables for people with disabilities. It is addressed to a restricted number of participants (15) and foresees the presence of users in order to develop a solution that is based on real needs and experiences. The activities ran over two weekends during the first edition held in 2019 and participants worked in teams autonomously with the support of OpenDot.

The organization and carrying out of Health&Care Summer School costs around 20,000 € covering materials, staff, travel expenses, catering during the events, fees for lecturers. Needs are selected considering their complexity in terms of required skills and knowledge, costs and feasibility of a solution in a short span (2 weeks).

In order to facilitate the co-design process between users and participants and deliver a first prototype of a careable at the end of the 2 weeks, OpenDot put

into writing the method conceived with TOG while creating customized aids for children with complex neurological diseases. The resulting toolkit with useful materials and templates can be used in all the future co-design activities, such as the Gantt chart or the storytelling canvas.

The first Summer School was financially supported by the Creative Europe programme within DDMP project. A new edition is foreseen in 2020.

Legal Guidance and follow-up

The legal guidance provided throughout Careables and for the Careable healthcare products would be more effective if carried out on a regular basis. This would allow an up-to-date guidance in line with the latest legislative developments in the field and it would enhance the continuous dissemination (e.g. through conferences, workshops, seminars, public talks or training) of the Careables research findings. Any research activity performed after the end of the project would need to be economically sustained (e.g. by a follow-up research project or other kind of research funds). Likewise, the execution of any further activity after the end of the project that is not covered by the project grant would need to be supported economically (which may vary in dependence of the specific situation, as an example an honorarium, the coverage of travel expenses, etc.).

11. Revenue/funding of activities

Finally, this chapter is dedicated to the income streams that should help us to cover the costs explained above.

To fund the platform and website hosting as well as staff costs, we want to approach foundations, private donors and public institutions. For trainings, we see the opportunity to take fees from training participants or their institutions.

We are researching these institutions, follow calls for application and aim to form partnerships to apply for matching ones. These include programs by foundations (like the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation¹⁹ or the Bosch Foundation²⁰),

¹⁹ <https://www.gatesfoundation.org/>

²⁰ <https://www.bosch-stiftung.de/en>

educational grants in innovative healthcare by companies (like Merck Group²¹ or Fresenius Medical Care²²) and charitable organizations like *Aktion Mensch*²³. We also support an initiative to create a more grassroots oriented fund for open source hardware prototypes.

In this chapter we concentrate on a plan on how our co-design sessions and the creation of more open hardware products can be funded.

Crowd-funding is a viable model of funding the development of future careables. The funds are needed to cover material costs in the development and secondly seen as a way to generate financial incentives for makers to initially create and/or to further develop careables. Furthermore, there are examples of successfully crowd-funding infrastructures of Makerspaces / Fab Labs needed to produce careables.

Different crowd-funding platforms are based on different models. Kickstarter is focusing primarily on the support of products or projects with a clear goal and end. For certain careables this is in line with the goals, and can be an option.

There are successfully funded examples of careables through Kickstarter such as Freedom Chair²⁴, Quad Stick²⁵, or Cane Minder²⁶.

Then again Kickstarter states in its rules "Projects can't fundraise for charity" and detail further "while non-profits are welcome to launch projects on Kickstarter, projects can't promise to raise funds to donate to a charity or cause". Furthermore, there are also regulations in place at Kickstarter that prohibit "any item claiming to diagnose, cure, treat, or prevent an illness or condition (whether via a device, app, book, nutritional supplement, or other means)." Thus, we see that we need to advise project creators to carefully consider whether Kickstarter is the most appropriate platform for their crowdfunding.

²¹ <https://www.merckgroup.com/en>

²² <https://www.freseniusmedicalcare.com/en/home/>

²³ <https://www.aktion-mensch.de/>

²⁴ Freedom Chair: the Adaptive All-Terrain Mobility Machine:

<https://www.kickstarter.com/projects/gogrit/freedom-chair-the-adaptive-all-terrain-mobility-ma>

²⁵ QuadStick: A Game Controller for Quadriplegics:

<https://www.kickstarter.com/projects/227850484/quadstick-a-game-controller-for->

²⁶ Cane Minder - Stop your cane from falling to the floor:

<https://www.kickstarter.com/projects/446025062/cane-minder>

The Berlin-based funding platform Betterplace.org on the other hand is focusing on charity donations, even with tax-deductible donation receipts for the supporters. The non-profit organization CADUS e.V. for example is successfully funding rent and materials needed for their Crisis Response Makerspace²⁷ where they develop humanitarian aid and med-tech solutions, such as a mobile hospital for Syria.

The platform Patreon²⁸ calls the supporters "Fans", their model is mainly person-centred. As a creator one can receive contributions from supporters. This could be a model for makers of careables, as well as for users of careables. Collecting funds through Patreon to e.g. pay for a new wheelchair is a common call for action on social media. At the same time we see rising criticism of this funding model, if it replaces dysfunctional social security and health insurance structures.

In the course of the project so far, valuable insights have been gained into the difficulties and potential of different financing mechanisms for open health solutions.

One serious difficulty is to cover the (often) considerable development costs through income from individual items or small series, such as Careables would most likely be. It should be borne in mind here that the time spent by technically experienced experts as co-creation partners for users is particularly associated with high costs. Technical experts, according to our previous knowledge, are usually only prepared to perform a certain amount of pro bono work. A typical limit is two full working days per month. This is not enough to develop marketable or small series products. It is only enough to develop prototypes, if at all. There is obviously a "chicken-and-egg problem" here: without sufficient working time of technical experts, no products are created that are attractive enough for financing partners to promise financing. And without financing partners no technical experts can be motivated for real product development projects.

In order to overcome this problem, it is not sufficient to address the manifold crowdfunding platforms and relevant foundations separately. It is not even enough to target these potential sources of financing for open health solutions

²⁷ <https://cadus.org/de/makerspace>

²⁸ <https://www.patreon.com/>

as a whole. Rather, what is needed is a novel process through which different potential financing partners are brought into debt and cleverly combined. With this in mind, we are currently developing the following financing process as a basis for the continuation of Careables activities. This process is illustrated in the following by means of an open health use-case.

1. **Phase: Ideation** – no funding needed as the ideation shall occur driven by intrinsic motivation and needs
2. **Phase: (co-funded) prototyping through co-creation** – a format called Open Health HACKademy serves as both an intense training (teaching design thinking and rapid prototyping skills) and a workshop sprint which leads to early prototypes of the ideated solutions for niche needs in health and wellbeing. Here, co-funding can be an appropriate way of creating sustainability: a consortium of partners shall cover the fixed costs of such sprints. Shared costs will bring down the costs needed to be covered from each partner to a reasonable amount.
 - a. Educational programmes: our Open Health HACKademies will be integrated into future Europe-wide and national educational funding programmes, such as the Lifelong Learning Programme, etc: [approx. 10,000 EUR funding per HACKademy](#)
 - b. Foundations (three foundations which want to support Open Health): [5,000 EUR per foundation = 15,000 EUR](#)
 - c. (Private) Business Angels / Impact Investors (20 selected Angels): [500 EUR per investor = 10,000 EUR](#)
3. **Phase: (funded) development of a mature prototype** – if a promising early prototype shall be taken to the next level, it does not need the entire consortium to co-finance it. Instead, one of the sources mentioned above shall take over the funding, based on his or her belief that the early prototype is so good that it justifies further development. Ideally, all of the above-mentioned financing sources have informed national level careables.org-groups about their limitations regarding financing specific concepts. [15,000 EUR might be a solid benchmark.](#)
4. **Phase: a mature prototype becomes a start-up's project** - as soon as the mature prototype is validated and it's clear that there is a critical number of individuals who would use the solution, too, founding a start-up is the right thing to do. Here, Business Angels might trade money for

up to 15% of equity in the start-up. Foundations might also be willing to support the early phase of a start-up operating around the Open Health solution that has been developed through this project.

In the following months the consortium will be further working on funding/partnership models for the different customer groups. During the remaining project period we will explore the opportunities in more detail and in a lean approach try to find evidence for our assumption as to what will work in the future to sustain the Careables activities in the future. The table below gives and overview of the main customer segments, the currently envisioned funding/partnership models and what we plan to test during the remaining funding period of the project.

Customer	Funding/Partnership Model	Pilots & Outlook
Public sector healthcare industry: hospitals, insurances, prostheses manufacturers, care homes social and health e.g.	Developing personalised offers for different customers; e.g. offering specific training programmes (from very basic co-design in healthcare to advanced courses in digital fabrication) that can be sold to different customer segments, such as hospitals or care homes, etc. Offering Hackathons or similar formats for specific customer segments, where the outcomes are first prototypes of Careables products	We will <ul style="list-style-type: none"> run a further training course for healthcare professionals (occupational therapists) in Italy (going beyond the first experiences) evaluate the possibilities to pilot exploitation of these trainings and hackathons also with hospitals in Germany known for their innovation, e.g. from the Bosch Foundation and rehabilitation centres) establish first contacts with prostheses manufacturers to gain insights into possibilities for a sustainable cooperation further develop our position towards commercial aspects, such as offering online advertisement space on the platform

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> elaborate a campaigning offer for health insurances and public institutions to show their support of a social project.
<p>Institutional donors: foundations, NGOs, private organisations, governmental organisations</p>	<p>Our first experiences with co-organising activities together with other projects or initiatives have been very positive and we want to build on them (e.g. HACKAdemy, Health & Care Summer School). We want to continue finding cooperation partners for these very specific activities.</p> <p>Also, we want to continue establishing partnerships with organisations working in healthcare technologies, such as Fieldready²⁹, Shuttleworth Foundation³⁰, MakeHealth Lab, etc. These organisations can help to promote the Careables platform and Careables activities.</p> <p>Individual consortium partners are strongly committed to continue their work in DIY health care by e.g. requesting new funding and sustaining the cooperations and in new constellations. The idea is that new projects will also foresee a small share of funding for sustaining the basic careables infrastructure.</p>	<p>We will</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> support the Humanitarian Design Challenge; this will be launched by Communitere³¹ and Fieldready in Nepal; Careables will be used for documentation and will offer our toolkits and knowledge base to be used during the Challenge (e.g. design for the events, etc.) launch events in parallel in 3 cities to promote open healthcare and gain visibility for Careables; for these events we will work with local companies, municipality, etc. to co-sponsor the events. send applications to local & global foundations for future Careables activities and gain evidence as to whether there is potential for Careables to attract foundations.

²⁹ <https://www.fieldready.org/>

³⁰ <https://www.shuttleworthfoundation.org/>

³¹ <https://nepal.communitere.org/>

<p>Individual donors: private supporters</p>	<p>For individuals we want to offer the possibilities to support individual Careables projects, either via crowdfunding portals or via donations.</p>	<p>We will</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • launch a donation campaign through betterplace³² for selected careables that will emerge as products from the upcoming HACKademy • explore the options to register as an NGO for a joint fundraising; this is however not a preferred option at the moment • evaluate the possibility of embedding a “donor-feature” (Patreon³³ or similar) within welder.app that contributes directly to project owners

12. Surplus

The Social Business Model Canvas methodology at the end asks where any surplus profits would be invested in or donated to. As Careables has a platform model and most of the partners are NGOs, in case of a surplus we would create new projects and help to create more new careables.

This means that any funds first are reinvested into the Careables platform. For example, if one co-design session or training provides excess funds, they should

³² <https://www.betterplace.org/en>

³³ <https://www.patreon.com/>

be put towards the overall platform to maximize the success of the entire Careables project. This would include advertising and marketing support etc.

After that, excess funds should also be put towards Careables ideas and future projects. For example, excess funds handed to one of the Fablabs or any Careables affiliate to continue and support the production of new Careables projects or advancements in existing products.

Further excess funds could also go towards makerspaces that are not yet affiliated with the project and are not able to fundraise themselves to carry out various workshops that align with the goals of the maker community and Careables project.

13. Summary and Outlook

As outlined in this deliverable we see great potential for the outcomes of this project to be sustainable. Most importantly, the commitment from the partners is very strong and there are already a number of concrete plans on how to continue the work after the official funding period. The social business model canvas, as we presented it in this document, is the starting point for our further work on sustainability.

The summary of our social business model canvas is presented in the following figure:

Social Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People (Expert Users, Healthcare professionals, Makers, engineers, designers, Trainers, Community and Co-Design Organisers, Legal Experts) - Financial means for personal, hosting and maintenance of platform and website - Access to digital fabrication machines <p><i>What resources will you need to run your activities? People, finance, access?</i></p>	<p>Key Activities</p> <p>Local events that establish collaboration between citizens with disabilities and their families, healthcare professionals and makers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Health Hackademy (Berlin) - MakeHealth Prototyping Series and Waag Trainings (Amsterdam) - Health&Care Summer School and Training for healthcare professionals (Milan) - ambitions in 3 QIG hubs <p>Global</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - general awareness raising campaign through social media - providing inspiring solutions - providing skills and knowledge - facilitating online and offline collaboration and creation of ideas - connecting with other communities and individuals, locally and globally - creating legal guidelines <p><i>What programme and non-programme activities will your organisation be carrying out?</i></p>	<p>Type of Intervention</p> <p>Local</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - events - resources in local languages <p>Global Online Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - careables.org Platform - welder.app Open Hardware Repository with Open Healthcare Map and documentation tool - Knowledge Base Materials, e.g. Toolkit for Co-Creation, Trainings on digital fabrication, Legal Guide <p><i>What is the format of your intervention? Is it a workshop? A service? A product?</i></p>	<p>Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users/patients and their families - Healthcare professionals - Makers, engineers, designers <p>Beneficiary</p> <p>Customer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - healthcare professionals and their employers (hospitals, care homes, manufacturers, health management,...) - institutional donors, philanthropic bodies - companies - individuals that are part of the beneficiaries or support them <p><i>Who are the people or organisations who will pay to address this issue?</i></p>	<p>Value Proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improve quality of life or services through human-centered innovation in healthcare and assistive technology - Improve the accessibility of open source products and knowledge to enable innovation beyond the topic of careables <p>Social Value Proposition</p> <p>Impact Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - impact assessment plan, continuous evaluation of 5 objectives with indicators and a concluding report - methods: qual. walkthroughs, questionnaires, statistics etc. <p><i>How will you show that you are creating social impact?</i></p>
<p>Partners + Key Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - careables consortium - patient organisations, associations of disabled people, healthcare providers, hospitals, MedTech industry - maker communities, maker networks, design organisations - philanthropic organisations - platforms with a special focus on health and care related topics <p><i>Who are the essential groups you will need to involve to deliver your programme? Do you need special access or permissions?</i></p>	<p>Channels</p> <p>Local</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - events, meetups, trainings, co-design sessions - ambassadors for health making - resources in local language: on websites of the partners, print materials <p>Global</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - partnerships - media and social media - direct outreach, applications <p><i>How are you reaching your beneficiaries and customers?</i></p>	<p>Surplus</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - any funds that are not reinvested into the platform and into more co-creation activities should go into the creation of more individual careables products <p><i>Where do you plan to invest your profits?</i></p>	<p>Revenue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - donors, philanthropic bodies - training: fees from participants/their employers - crowdfunding <p><i>Break down your revenue sources by %</i></p>	<p>Customer Value Proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reduce the cost of innovation in public healthcare system - fulfil corporate social responsibilities - good feeling for supporting a cause that directly benefit individuals <p><i>What do your customers want to get out of this initiative?</i></p>
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - biggest expenditure independent of scale: careables platform (server hosting, bandwidth, maintenance) - can be scaled+distributed as funding sources allow: community involvement, trainings and co-creation activities <p><i>What are your biggest expenditure areas? How do they change as you scale up?</i></p>				

In order to turn these strategies into reality the second half of the project is crucial for piloting some of the planned activities and preparing the next phase, after the EC funding. In the next months we will elaborate our partnership models for the different customer groups and initiate some piloting activities with our partners. E.g. we will explore how certain careables may gain funding from crowd-donation sites or how we can establish partnerships with other initiatives in the healthcare and health technology sector. Our experiences with co-organising targeted training offers at the intersection of open healthcare, co-design and digital fabrication have been very promising so far and we continue to explore more along those lines.

We will work on the documentation of all our activities for lasting impact and provide descriptions of the methodology for others to copy and re-use. Our philosophy is not only to offer a platform for sharing open healthcare solutions, but also to share our experiences and methodology with others. Thus, other organisations might want to open local chapters of Careables and implement our approach in local engagement. This is going to be further explored by each partner based on the contacts we have established across organisations.